

Appendix B - List of Issues Leading to Machine Learning Code Technical Debt

I. APPENDIX

Table I consolidates the reported issues leading to ML code TD within each ML life cycle phase and their descriptions.

TABLE I: Issues leading to ML code TD per ML life cycle phase and their descriptions.

Phase	Issue	Description
Data Collection	Inappropriate/Wrong data consumption	Consuming irrelevant or unfiltered data hinders analysis with noise and redundant information.
	Inappropriate/Wrong data integration	Combining data sources incorrectly can lead to errors and misinterpretations.
	Incomplete/Insufficient data consumption	Analyzing only a limited portion of the necessary data could result in missed insights.
	Incomplete/Insufficient data integration	Partial integration can result in biased insights and incomplete patterns.
Data Pre-processing	Missing data integration	Omitting certain data sources can lead to incomplete datasets and missed critical information.
	Inappropriate/Wrong feature selection	Selecting irrelevant or redundant features may overcomplicate the model and introduce unnecessary variables.
	Inappropriate/Wrong missing value identification	Misidentifying existing values as missing (or vice versa) may compromise data quality, skewing analysis.
	Inappropriate/Wrong outlier identification	Classifying normal data as outliers can lead to erroneous conclusions.
	Inappropriate/Wrong pre-processing scaling	Using inappropriate scaling techniques may alter relationships within the data, misleading model performance.
	Inappropriate/Wrong rebalancing	Applying inappropriate resampling techniques may worsen data imbalance or introduce artifacts, leading to deformed results.
	Inappropriate/Wrong removal of inconsistent data	Removing valid but seemingly inconsistent data without proper assessment could reduce the dataset's completeness and harm analysis.
	Incomplete/Insufficient feature selection	Omitting key features can weaken the model's robustness.
	Incomplete/Insufficient missing value identification	Identifying only some missing values can lead to incomplete data preparation and potentially impact model accuracy.
	Incomplete/Insufficient outlier identification	Detecting only some outliers, rather than comprehensively analyzing the dataset, may leave potential biases in place.
	Incomplete/Insufficient pre-processing scaling	Inconsistently scaling only certain parts of the data can lead to biases, affecting model interpretations and results.
	Incomplete/Insufficient removal of inconsistent data	Partially removing inconsistent data without thorough analysis may leave residual errors, reducing data integrity.
	Missing features selection	Not selecting relevant features can introduce noise into the model, complicating analysis and potentially reducing predictive accuracy.
	Missing missing value identification	Overlooking missing values could lead to biased analysis and affect the reliability of conclusions or predictions.
	Missing outlier identification	Not identifying outliers can lead to overlooking data errors or unique patterns that might otherwise provide valuable insights for the model.
Missing pre-processing scaling	Neglecting scaling can distort relationships within the data, especially in distance-based algorithms, impacting model accuracy.	
Missing rebalancing	Ignoring data imbalances may result in biased predictions, with the model potentially favoring majority classes.	
Missing removal of inconsistent data	Neglecting inconsistencies can introduce errors and affect model reliability.	
Model Creation and Training	Inappropriate/Wrong hyperparameter tuning	Using wrong parameters can misalign the model's focus, reducing efficiency and accuracy.
	Inappropriate/Wrong splitting of training/test/validation data	Improper data splits can skew results, leading to biased or inaccurate conclusions.
	Incomplete/Insufficient hyperparameter tuning	Improperly tuning parameters can lead to overfitting or underfitting, impacting performance.
	Incomplete/Insufficient testing candidate algorithm possibilities	Trying a limited set of algorithms may result in missed opportunities for optimization.
	Missing hyperparameter tuning	Omitting hyperparameter tuning can leave the model suboptimized, impacting its performance.
	Missing splitting training/test/validation data	Not splitting data into training, test, and validation sets may result in overfitting, compromising model reliability.
Model Evaluation	Missing testing candidate algorithm possibilities	Omitting algorithm testing may limit the ability to find the optimal model.
	Incomplete/Insufficient evaluation metric selection	Using non-optimal metrics may mask weaknesses in the model, giving a skewed impression of accuracy.